

Synthesis of Pyrazoles and Fused Pyrazoles. Novel Synthesis of Pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole, Thieno[2,3-*c*]pyrazole and Pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine Derivatives

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3-Methyl-1-thiocarbamoylpyrazol-5-one (1) reacted with *p*-methylphenacyl bromide to give 3-methyl-1-(4-thiazol-2-yl)pyrazol-5-one (2). Compounds 1 and 2 were reacted with reagents such as α -cyanocinnamyl aldehyde, elemental sulphur/malononitrile, benzenediazonium chloride, pyrazol-5-yl-diazonium chloride, malononitrile, and ethyl acetoacetate to afford pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles (4, 6), pyrazole (7), thieno[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (9), pyrazoles (12, 15), pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (10) and pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine (11) derivatives respectively.

Pyrazole derivatives are used as medicine¹. In continuation of our work on pyrazoles and fused pyrazoles², we would like to report here the synthesis of some new pyrazoles, fused pyrazoles and pyrazolythiazole derivatives.

3-Methyl-1-thiocarbamoylpyrazol-5-one (1) was reacted with *p*-methylphenacyl bromide to produce 3-methyl-1-(4-*p*-tolylthiazol-2'-yl)pyrazol-5-one (2). Compounds 1 and 2 behaved differently towards α -cyanocinnamyl aldehyde (3). Thus, 1 underwent fission during its addi-

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

tion to 3 result the pyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivative (4) and thiocarbamic acid (5). On the other hand, when 2 was added to 3, 1-thiazolylpyranol[2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivative (6) was formed (Scheme 1).

In support of structure 4 for the reaction product, compound 4 was synthesised in two steps. Condensation of 1 with benzaldehyde yielded the 4-benzylidene derivative (7). The latter, reacted with malononitrile in ethanolic piperidine solution to give 4. On the other hand, compound 4 was found to be identical with an authentic sample prepared according to the reported method³. Thiocarbamic

acid resulting from the reaction of **1** with **3** could be separated via its reaction with *p*-methylphenacyl bromide to produce *p*-methylphenacyl thiocyanate (**8**). The latter was found to be identical with an authentic sample prepared from the reaction of *p*-methylphenacyl bromide with potassium thiocyanate.

Also, compound **2** was reacted with a mixture of elemental sulphur and malononitrile in ethanolic triethylamine solution to afford thieno[3,2-*c*]pyrazole derivative (**9**)⁴. Similarly, **1** was reacted with malononitrile in ethanolic piperidine solution to give pyranol[2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivative (**10**). Structure of **10** was confirmed from its mass spectrum (*m/z* 164), ir and ¹H nmr spectral data. On the other hand, pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine (**11**) was formed via fusion of **1** with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of ammonium acetate. Compounds **1** and **2** were coupled with benzenediazonium chloride to produce the corresponding 4-phenylhydrazones **12** and **13** respectively. Compound **13** could be obtained via reaction of **12** with *p*-methylphenacyl bromide. Similarly, compound **1** was coupled with 3-phenyl-5-pyrazolyldiazonium chloride (**14**) to give 5-pyrazolylhydrazone (**15**). The coupling products **12**, **13** and **15** (Scheme 2).

Experimental

M.p.s were determined on an electrothermal apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectrum (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam sp 1100 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆, CDCl₃ or acetone-*d*₆) on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer. Elemental analyses were carried out at Microanalytical Centre of Cairo University. Elemental analyses of the compounds were found satisfactory.

3-Methyl-1-thiocarbamoylpyrazole-5-one (**1**) synthesised as described in the literature⁵.

3-Methyl-1-(4'-*p*-tolylthiazol-2'-yl)pyrazol-5-one (**2**) : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and *p*-methylphenacyl bromide (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then made alkaline with NH₄OH and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (80%), m.p. 135; *m/z* 271.

6-Amino-3-methyl-4-phenyl-1H,4H-pyranol[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-5-carbonitrile (**4**) : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and α -cyanocinnamitrile (**3**) in ethanol (30 ml) containing 2 drops of piperidine was refluxed for 5 h. The solid formed was crystallised from EtOH/DMF as white crystals, which was found to be identical with sample prepared according to the literature procedure³.

p-Methylphenacylthiocyanate (**8**) : *p*-Methylphenacyl bromide (0.01 mol) was refluxed with the filtrate from the above reaction for 3 h, then poured in cold water containing NH₄OH. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as yellowish crystals.

6-Amino-3-methyl-4-phenyl-1-(4'-*p*-tolylthiazol-2-yl)-1H,4H-pyranol[2,3-*c*]pyrazol-5-carbonitrile (**6**) : A mixture of **2** (0.01 mol) and α -cyanocinnamitrile (**3**; 0.001 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) containing 2 drops of piperidine was

refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in acidified cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (75%), m.p. 175°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 240, 3 200 (NH₂), 2 200 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ 1.70 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.40 (3H, s br, CH₃), 5.2 (s br, D₂O exchangeable, NH₂), 7.00–8.00 (11H, m, ArH, thiazole-H4 and pyran-H4).

4-Benzylidene-3-methyl-1-thiocarbamoylpyrazol-5-one (**7**) : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (20 ml) containing sodium acetate (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol/dioxane, (85%), m.p. 200°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 390–3 180 (NH₂), 1 640 cm⁻¹ (CO).

6-Amino-4-imino-3-methyl-1H,4H-pyranol[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (**10**) : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) and malononitrile (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) containing 2 drops of piperidine, was refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in acidified cold water and the solid formed was crystallised from ethanol (75%), m.p. 200°; *m/z* 164.

6,7-Dihydro-3,4-dimethyl-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridin-6-one (**11**) : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (0.01 mol) and ammonium acetate (5 g) was heated at 140° for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in water and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (85%), m.p. 240°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 200–2 500 (NH₂, NH), 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 2.10 (5H, s, CH₃ and NH₂); decreased by 2 protons after shaking with D₂O), 5.40 (2H, s, pyran-H3 and NH; decreased by 1 proton after shaking with D₂O), 10.70 (s br, D₂O exchangeable, NH).

Compound **12** : A solution of benzenediazonium chloride (0.01 mol) was added gradually to a cold solution of **1** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) containing sodium (0.01 mol) with continuous stirring. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from chloroform, (79%), m.p. 300°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 390–3 375 (NH₂, NH), 1 690 cm⁻¹ (CO); δ 2.40 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.71 (5H, m, ArH), 9.30 (2H, s br, D₂O exchangeable, NH).

Compound **13** : Compound **12** (0.01 mol) was refluxed with *p*-methylphenacyl bromide (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in acidified cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from EtOH/DMF, (75%), m.p. 235°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 390 (CN), 1 665 cm⁻¹ (CO); δ 2.44 (6H, s, 2 $\times$ CH₃), 7.50–8.50 (10H, m, ArH and thiazole-H4), 13.68 (1H, s br, D₂O exchangeable, NH).

Compound **15** : A solution of diazotised 5-amino-3-phenylpyrazole (0.01 mol) was added gradually to a cold solution of compound **1** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) containing (0.01 mol) sodium acetate, with continuous stirring. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 230°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 380–3 340 (NH₂, NH), 1 665 (CO), 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

5-Amino-3-methyl-1-(4'-*p*-tolylthiazol-2-yl)-1H-thieno[3,2-*c*]pyrazol-6-carbonitrile (**9**) : Compound **2** (0.01 mol) was refluxed with malononitrile (0.01 mol) and sulphur

(0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) containing triethylamine (1 ml) for 5 h. The reaction mixture was then poured in acidified cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (75%), m.p. 200°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 220, 3 160 (NH₂), 2 220 cm⁻¹ (CN); δ 2.15 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 7.8 (5H, m, ArH and thiazole-H), 12.40 (2H, s br, D₂O exchangeable, NH₂).

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